

USING PICTURE ESSAY IN DEVELOPING THE SPEECH OF PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT: *This article describes the use of pictorial essays, its importance, methods of organization, and the advantages of using multimedia in the process of teaching students' speech in primary-grade mother tongue and reading literacy classes.*

KEY WORDS: *speech development, picture essay, pictures, educational tools, exhibition, independent thinking, oral and written.*

ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ЭССЕ В КАРТИНКАХ В РАЗВИТИИ РЕЧИ УЧАЩИХСЯ НАЧАЛЬНЫХ КЛАССОВ

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АННОТАЦИЯ: *В данной статье описывается использование изобразительного эссе, его значение, методы организации, а также преимущества использования мультимедиа в процессе обучения речи учащихся на уроках родного языка и грамотности чтения в начальных классах.*

КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА: *развитие речи, фотоэссе, картинки, учебные пособия, выставка, самостоятельное мышление, устная и письменная речь.*

BOSHLANG‘ICH SINFI O‘QUVCHILARINING NUTQINI O‘STIRISHDA RASMLI INSHOLARDAN FOYDALANISH

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ANNOTATSIYA: *Ushbu maqolada boshlang‘ich sinfi ona tili va o‘qish savodxonligi darslarida o‘quvchilarning nutqini o‘qtirish jarayonida rasmlar insholardan foydalanish, uning ahamiyati, tashkil etish usullari, unda multimedialardan foydalaishning afzalliklari yoritilgan.*

KALIT SO‘ZLAR: *nutq o‘stirish, rasmlar, ta‘lim vositalari, ko‘rgazma, mustaqil fikrlash, og‘zaki va yozma.*

One of the important types of essays written in elementary grades is the essay based on visuality, based on how young students understand what they see, and their worldviews.

One such essay is the picture essay. Taking into account the age characteristics of elementary school students, pictorial essays are important as they encourage creativity and increase their imagination.

In Uzbekistan, schools are rapidly being equipped with computer equipment and connected to the Internet. Lessons are organized independently by the teacher with the most modern visual aids. It is necessary to use computer equipment such as computer, projector, screen. Teachers create modern methodological developments and media lessons using the materials they have previously prepared.

It is not a secret for anyone that in most cases, students learn computer and related technologies faster than the teacher. This is natural. It is a pity if the teacher does not know the computer and does not want to know it even at the elementary level.

Therefore, the current educational process requires reading and researching hundreds of pages of manuals on the effective use of modern computer equipment, and imparting the latest knowledge using ICT to our flawless future generation.

Still a reasonable question as to whether it is possible to use ICT in some regions. But the possibilities of using slides, pictures, schemes in paper versions or portable projectors is a natural situation that exists everywhere. This requires teachers to love their profession and be responsible. At the very least, it is possible to increase the activity of students by using CDs on television, showing various clips, holiday events or cartoons that encourage logical research, puzzles, riddles.

The organization of classes using new, unfamiliar methods for the young generation, who are still adapting to the educational process from playing activities, encourages them to further increase their interest in education, to develop creativity, independent thinking, and ambition.

An essay based on a picture is often held in schools, because the picture serves to enrich children's speech creativity and imagination. The picture affects children's intuition, reveals aspects of life that have not yet been encountered in the child's experience. The picture also helps students to deepen their understanding of familiar events.

There are three main types of picture essays:

- an essay in the style of a story written based on a series of pictures or a pictorial plan;
- an essay in the style of a story written based on a picture with a plot, which encourages readers to think and hypothesize;

- write a picture essay (describe a picture)

Students are taught to write a pictorial essay (describing a picture) first based on a series of pictures, then based on a single picture.

The topic is the subject of the essay and constitutes its content. Depending on the topic, the materials, evidence, and events reflected in the essay are selected. The correctness and completeness of the essay depends on how the teacher formulates the topic and how the students understand it.

Choosing a topic while working on an essay, and determining the topic of an oral and written essay plays an important role in its planning.

Students learn to cover the topic from the 1st grade. They make a topic sentence. For example, they talk about the spring air, about their native village (city), about a cowardly rabbit, a cunning fox. Then, based on the questions, they compose a few sentences on a topic and write it down. It is helpful to recommend a topic that is as narrow as possible for the essay. The topic "Autumn" is a very broad topic for students, in which the student can write about autumn in general, about things to do in autumn, he writes - he does not know the exact limit of his words. Readers can be recommended autumn topics such as "On one of the autumn days", "We picked apples in the garden", "The hero I love", "Late autumn garden scenery".

In addition to giving a topic and demanding to cover it when working on an oral and written essay, it is also possible to recommend collecting material first and forming a topic based on these collected materials. For example, it is recommended to observe nature and collect material in late autumn, the observations will end with writing an essay on "Late autumn". [Textbook for the 4th grade "Mother language"] In this, the students fully cover the topic.

We can use different forms of educational tools in the learning process of primary education. Through them, the rules of correct writing, word meanings, characters of the work, analysis of their good and bad characteristics and drawing the necessary conclusions are the main visual tools for the native language and reading classes. Because elementary school students believe and practice what they see more than what they hear.

Video clips with picture alphabets, audio magnetic tapes of poems written dedicated to letters are also very effective in introducing sounds to students. For this, letters are taken separately. A color picture of the object is placed on its upper part and a poem representing it flows. Its name is written with a dot instead of the studied sound. Questions and answers conducted with students about the given object or subject, the plot, are also aimed at forming a coherent and written speech.

A moving exhibition is of great importance in organizing logical exercises, mainly grouping objects. Pictures depicting forest animals are shown in sequence. Having students repeat names or rhymes together can help them develop speaking skills and help them develop the skills to express their understanding in writing.

Based on the decision and requirements of the Ministry of Public Education "On creating a new generation of textbooks", new textbooks "Mother language and reading literacy book" were published for primary classes. These textbooks have a number of requirements. "The new generation of textbooks, first of all, it is necessary that the educational tasks given in it should be structured in such a way as to teach the student to work actively, as well as to think independently and creatively," says the manual on the creation of new textbooks. From this beside, decoration in terms of time requirements according to to be need. So 1st grade "Reading literacy book" textbooks are also marked requirements according to to be need _ Current in the day lesson in processes Multimedia general education programs development center All of the 1st grades by from the sciences prepared multimedia textbooks from 2014 work is being released and use for recommendation done.

Because, the textbook multimedia of the textbook requirements answer gives, but lesson during only from him use students scientific terms, in them was born to questions answer give can't, at all lesson process live organize to reach limiting puts This point of view we mean from the textbook initial in classes independent things technical from tools use for source in the we used Results very good In students in the textbook included quizzes, riddles and puzzles, video assignments from cartoons independent things organize in reaching important tool it has been.

Through the monitor demonstration done to pictures looking four - five speaking text composition, oral story composition, question - answer transfer the work of types use can _ For example: 1st grade "Reading Literacy" in the book "Ilm - Aql chiragi" "Computer" section in the "light" section prepared video image, puzzle students independent to search calling with, new knowledge mastering and independent ground for their thinking creates.

Therefore, the use of oral and written essays organized through pictorial, i.e., visual means in elementary grades is an important tool for developing the ability of students to be creative and independent, to express their ideas, conclusions, and independent thoughts verbally and in writing without hesitation.

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